

COVID^X

COVID EXPONENTIAL PROGRAMME

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D3.1 – OUTREACH MATERIAL

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Authors	Marill Mona, Arregui Blanca, Jose Gonzalez (AUS)
Reviewers	Antonio Damasceno (F6S)

Abstract	Compilation of initial outreach material supporting the COVID-X dissemination and communication plans.
Keywords	Communication, dissemination, outreach, target audience

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Project co-funded by the European Commission in the H2020 Programme		
Nature of the deliverable:		DEC
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	X
CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO	Confidential project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

COVID-X Outreach Material is essential for executing both communication and dissemination plans of the project. It is designed and addressed for specified target audiences that are direct or indirect beneficiaries of the COVID-X Program. These target audiences include Tech Companies providing data or AI solutions tackling COVID-19, Healthcare providers that implement the exponential innovation in the care process of coronavirus patients as well as all related European, national and local networks of eHealth SMEs and of Healthcare organizations.

COVID-X Outreach material includes a set communication tools, essentially a common methodology for promotion, a set of specific digital channels and branded promotional material available online and offline. In addition, it includes specific elements used for dissemination, namely project materials, digital resources as well as events.

This document details all outreach tools created during the first project month and how these contribute to implement the dissemination and communication plans. These tools are living elements that are continuously adapted and refined as COVID-X Program moves forwards, taking also into account in the changing project context, notably the European coronavirus situation.

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TERMS & ABBREVIATIONS

COVID-X	COVID-X eXponential Programme, Innovation action supported by the European Commission in the framework of the EC call SC1-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020-2B
AI	Artificial Intelligence
Accelerate	Transfer technical, business, and ethical knowledge
OC	Open Calls
Single player	<i>See Single Solution</i>
Single Solution (SS)	Open call line for technology providers
Team Solution (TS)	Open call line for clinical partners working in a team with technology providers
Technology provider	Company, a start-up or a SME, that has developed an eHealth certified solution to tackle clinical challenges of the Covid-19
Tech company	see Technology Provider
Clinical partner, COVID-X Pilot site	Member of COVID-X consortium. Hospital, clinic, primary care centre or other testbed taking care of diagnosis, treatment, monitoring and/ or recovery of COVID-19 patients. Entity with data, resources and infrastructure for the piloting of the SME solution.
Healthcare provider	Third party. Hospital, clinic, primary care centre or other testbed taking care of diagnosis, treatment, monitoring and/ or recovery of COVID-19 patients. Entity with data, resources, and infrastructure for the piloting of the SME solution.
eHealth certified solution	Market-oriented and market-ready solutions starting at TRL 7 with [or in the process] CE marking. Scouted in the Open Calls and the selected ones will join the Acceleration programme.
Validate, validation	Deploy the AI / data solution in collaboration with real-world clinical partners
Pilot	Deploy the AI / data solution in collaboration with real-world clinical partners
TRL	Technology readiness level

1. GENERAL METHODOLOGY

This document gathers all elements designed and released to execute the dissemination and communication plans, including the project website, logo, presentation and documentation templates, social medical channels, and initial PR design.

1.1 Objectives

COVID-X program aims at growing brand awareness, enhancing key stakeholder adoption, creating buzz, and establishing a loyal following. The communication activities, carried as a part of WP3 COVID-19 Innovation, targets to attract and select high quality applicants for the COVID-X program recruiting in two Open calls. The dissemination actions will build effective awareness of the results.

AUS leads the T3.1 Communication & Outreach, running throughout the project duration. It defines and monitors the implementation of the Communication & Dissemination Plans. All partners are involved in implementing Communication & Dissemination actions to reach out a critical mass of target audience in all partner countries, and beyond, as well as to leverage the partners’ existing communities and networks.

Measure	Indicators	Target
Publications	Peer-reviewed scientific research publications in international journals	10
	Peer-reviewed publications and presentations in international conferences	10
	Scientific and Technical Publications (e.g. articles, blog posts)	150+
Events	No. of scientific events participated	15+
	No. of non-scientific events participated	30+
Webinars	No. of webinars organised	20+
	No. of participants (total)	500+
Project Website	No. of visitors (monthly average)	1,000+
Printed Material	No. of hard copies (e.g. flyers) distributed	3,000+
Social media	Size of the online community (by the end of the project)	6,000+
	No. of impressions (monthly average)	600+
Videos	No. of videos produced	3
Newsletters	No. of newsletters contributed/released	9
Fire chats	No. of motivational talks organised	6

FIGURE 1: COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION KPI GOALS

1.2 Target Audience

To start engaging with the identified target audience, partners have created an internal work document listing the COVID-X Stakeholders. It lists gathers target groups from the key sectors including individual companies, Start-Up and SME communities, healthcare providers, innovation & health ecosystems, as well as Policy makers. Under the supervision of AUS team, this table is updated continuously considering the changing European stakeholder landscapes and new rising initiatives.

Type	Name	Country	Website
Start-Up	Start-Up Bootcamp	International	https://www.startupbootcamp.org/
Tech-SME	MSing with Trauma	Europe	https://www.linkedin.com/company/msing-with-trauma/
Tech-SME	Hexigone	Europe	https://www.hexigone.com/
Start-Up	Babilon Health	Europe	https://www.babylonhealth.com/
Start-Up	Mind Maze	Europe & US	https://www.mindmaze.com/
Start-Up	Cera Care	Europe & US	https://ceracare.co.uk/
Start-Up	Benevolent AI	Europe & US	https://www.benevolent.com
Start-Up	KRY	Europe	https://career.kry.se/
Start-Up	AMRA	Europe & US	https://www.amramedical.com/
Start-Up	Castor	Europe	https://www.castoredc.com/
Tech-SME	DECSIS / BDVA TF 8 SME	Portugal	https://en.decsis.eu/ https://www.bdva.eu/task-force-8
Tech-SME	Lucentia Lab	Spain	https://lucentialab.com/en/big-data-applications-and-business-intelligence/

FIGURE 2: SCREENSHOT OF COVID-X STAKEHOLDERS TABLE

2. COMMUNICATION PLAN

The goal is to promote the project activities, with a special focus on the 2 Open Calls targeting eHealth Tech Companies and Healthcare providers dealing with COVID-19 patients. The communication plan establishes a strategy to reach out a critical mass.

2.1 Promotion Methodology

Communication campaigns will be implemented throughout the 24 project months to engage with target audiences. These campaigns are built upon the **Promotion MIX** that focuses on creating awareness and persuading the audience to engage with the project. This strategy includes four key action elements: **personal selling, digital channels, promotional material, and branding.**

Personal Selling

All partners will engage with personal selling campaigns from the 1st of December 2020 onwards.

Email campaigns

As soon as the Open Calls are launched, the identified stakeholders are contacted with **email campaigns**. AUS will create **mailing lists** promoting the both open calls to the target groups, namely Tech Providers, data-driven EU communities as well as healthcare providers. **Harmonized message templates** adapted for each target group are ready in English, local partners oversee translations and adaptations when necessary.

One-to-One meetings

These meetings target specific key individuals as a follow-up of an email exchange or an event. These are especially important for the interested **clinical parties**.

Digital Channels

Ever before the project kick-off, COVID-X has a structured and **continuous online presence** that includes a dedicated **website, partners' online media, social channels** and regular digital publications.

Project website

COVID-X website¹ does not only focus on **the generic promotion** of the project, but it is also **designed to attract Tech Providers** to get interested in the program and to join the Open Call. It includes general information about the project, consortium, EC references and most importantly key information about the Open Call application process. In addition, it displays calls to action towards the F6S Application platform where the OC applications are submitted. Finally, the website shares project results highlighting the project impact as well as it features related news.

The website will be structured in the following pages:

¹ Cf. <http://www.covid-x.eu/>

- **Home:** landing page of the site, providing high-level information about the program and the open call.

FIGURE 3: COVID-X WEBSITE - HOME

- **Program:** page describing the context and the specific of COVID-X program; i.e. funding, acceleration and COVID-X Sandbox. In addition, the page contains references to the consortium of the project, with relevant links.

COVID-X Program

COVID-X takes the battle against coronavirus to a new level, bridging the gap between the European digital sector and healthcare providers. The program will unlock the full capacity of Artificial Intelligence and Data Technology solutions to overcome COVID-19 Challenges, fast-tracking projects to market and save lives.

Financial Support & Validation

COVID-X provides direct funding to validate 30+ Data Technology Solutions ready-to-market [TRL7+] in real-world clinical sites.

Products must have CE marking or in the process to be certified.

Single Player
100K €

x1 EU Tech Company
* Validation at one of COVID-X Clinical Sites
- Istituto Clinico Humanitas [Italy]
- Hospital Clinico San Carlos [Spain]
- Karolinska Institute [Sweden]

Team Player
150K €

x1 EU Tech Company
+ x1 EU Healthcare Provider
validating the solution
- Hospitals
- Clinics
- Primary care centres
- Telehealth operators
- Assisted Living Facilities

Acceleration

Selected ideas will be fast-tracked to market, launching their EXPONENTIAL impact to save

FIGURE 4: COVID-X WEBSITE - PROGRAM

- **Apply:** page dedicated to present the information about the open call, including details on the clinical challenges defined and embedded into 3 categories (Diagnosis, Prognosis and Follow-up), the clinical partners, and key references to documentation and dates.

COVID-X PILOT SITES

Milan (Italy)
Istituto Clinico Humanitas

Madrid (Spain)
Hospital Clinico San Carlos

Stockholm (Sweden)
Karolinska Institute

Download the Open Call Documents KIT [HERE](#)

Timeline

FIGURE 5: COVID-X WEBSITE – APPLY

- **News:** page dedicated to present blog post and announce publications from the project.
- **Awards:** this page will display information about the projects selected from the Open Call 1. It will be created and added to the website as soon as this information is available.

Additionally, the website also takes into consideration other elements such as:

- **European funded project claim:** COVID-X receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016065. The content of this website does not represent the opinion of the European Union, and the European Union is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content
- **Cookie Policy:** COVID-X leverages the GDPR-complaint platform www.cookiebot.com for managing cookies
- **Privacy Policy:** See [Annex 1](#)
- **Terms of Use:** See [Annex 2](#)

F6S Platform

The platform **promotes the COVID-X open calls** in its network composed of 1.3 million start-ups and 1.7 million entrepreneurs. It also gives access to Open call application forms and submissions. The specific page created for the project is www.f6s.com/covid-x

Partners' websites

Each project partner has their own website sharing information about COVID-X to their community.

www.f6s.com

www.australo.org

civitta.com

bosonit.com

www.intrasoft-intl.com

www.8bellsresearch.com

www.upm.es

www.comunidad.madrid/servicios/salud

www.humanitas.net

<https://ki.se/en>

Social Media

COVID-X has a constant online presence in the **dedicated social media channels**. It shares daily relevant news, articles, and project updates to generate traffic and get an increasing number of impressions.

The marketing strategy in each of the channels is different due to the idiosyncrasy of each social network.

- Twitter: [@TheCovidX](https://twitter.com/TheCovidX)

FIGURE 6: COVID-X TWITTER PROFILE

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/covid-x>

FIGURE 7: COVID-X LINKEDIN PROFILE

In Twitter, the strategy consists of defining posting lists by specific topics (Artificial Intelligence, Data and health, Digital solutions, EU COVID-19 Programmes, Healthcare Institutions, Research & Innovation, etc.) and connecting relevant profiles for each list to reach out a critical mass of audience interested in these topics. COVID-X Twitter account follows other relevant profiles, and it publishes updates related to the COVID-X Program topics.

FIGURE 8: COVID-X TWITTER LISTS

In LinkedIn, COVID-X promotes the page among our contacts acting in the COVID-X fields (data solutions, AI, eHealth, COVID-19...), and the project participates in third-party conversations about these challenges. Moreover, the community strategy identifies other LinkedIn users who have shared COVID-X posts.

Posting plan:

The consortium has created an internal table listing the main topics to post about (eHealth, Innovation, Tech Start-Ups, Digital, Data and Health, etc), with the hashtags related to them. Also, a posting calendar for each day of the week defined the daily activity on Twitter and LinkedIn.

The chosen hashtags are: **#GameOn**, **#TheCovidX** and **#DatavCovid**, among others, but these are used systematically in all social media publications.

In addition, COVID-X will leverage traffic from [SERMAS](#), [Humanitas](#), [KI](#), [F6S](#) Social channels.

The social media strategy started with creating a community in LinkedIn and Twitter.

Newsletters

The main goal is to promote both Open Calls, therefore a dedicated newsletter will not be the most efficient way to reach out to the target audience. Therefore, the project will use already existing newsletters to promote the COVID-X actions, such as partners' newsletters, the EC newsletter, and other related projects.

Press Releases

These publications will communicate to all stakeholders the essential milestones of the project, such as the project kick-off, open call publications and key achievements. The press releases are shared among the partners' networks of customers and members (via their websites and social channels).

The joint press release launched for the project kick-off can be found in [Annex 3](#) of this document and in Zenodo².

General Spreading

Leveraging online publication platforms to reach out to a broader audience including professionals in healthcare but also non-specialized audience with an interest in emerging technologies applied to the pandemic. All promotional material and press releases will be used for this action. Partners keep an internal list about all identified publication platforms where information, articles, and news about COVID-X could be published.

Promotional material

On the top of all digital channels, COVID-X outreach kit includes promotional materials that can be used during meetings, conferences, and events. These are living documents that will be updated throughout the project.

Printed material

These are reference material, especially printed flyers, and one-pagers, used in event and meeting participation. Yet, given the current context of only online meetings and events, this is not an urgent action point.

Slide deck & One pagers

These are digital documents that are eye-catching to quickly draw attention and share the visitation and the specific objectives of the project. The first version will be created for the launch of OC#1 to be used in personal selling and digital channels.

² COVID-X Press Release #1. https://zenodo.org/record/4275652/files/COVID-X_Press_Release_Nov2020.pdf

COVID^X
DATA vs COVID-19
GAME ON

DEFEATING COVID-19 WITH DATA SOLUTIONS

OPEN CALL COVID-19 Data Technology Solutions, ready-to-market [TRL 7+] with CE marking [or in process]

APPLY NOW

DEADLINE
27 January 2021, 17:00 CET

MORE INFO
www.covid-x.eu

FUNDING

- 100 K€**
X1 EU TECH COMPANY
*VALIDATION AT COVID-X CLINICAL SITES
- 150 K€**
X1 EU TECH COMPANY + X1 EU HEALTHCARE PROVIDER

ACCELERATION PROGRAM

- DATA SANDBOX
- TECHNICAL SUPPORT
- ETHICAL VALIDATION
- BUSINESS COACHING

SINGLE PLAYER + **TEAM PLAYER**

DIAGNOSIS PROGNOSIS FOLLOW-UP

FOLLOW US @TheCovidX company/covid-x #GameON

COVID-X has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016065.

FIGURE 9: COVID-X ONE PAGER OPEN CALL 1

Branding

COVID-X Program has a defined brand that will be fine-tuned throughout the project. All communication and dissemination items are aligned with this brand.

FIGURE 10: COVID-X LOGO

FIGURE 11: COVID-X ICON (1:1 RATIO)

The initial guidelines have been defined and applied to graphical elements such as:

- Banners: used in all kind of references and optimised for platforms accordingly

FIGURE 12: COVID-X MAIN BANNER

FIGURE 13: COVID-X TWITTER BANNER (OPTIMISED AT 3:1 RATIO)

- [Presentation template](#): this template will be used for all COVID-X presentations.

 COVID-X receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101016065

FIGURE 14: COVID-X PRESENTATION TEMPLATE

- **Deliverable template**: this document enables to harmonize the layout of all project documentation.
- **Brand guidelines**: this document serves as main reference for using the fonts, colours and other visual elements to be used in the project related communication.
- **Social media post template**: this document helps to align all social media publications with the project branding.

FIGURE 15: COVID-X SOCIAL MEDIA POST TEMPLATE

3. DISSEMINATION PLAN

The objective is to promote the COVID-X program outcomes throughout the project duration. This plan defines the actions and channels envisioned to build effective awareness about the results and to engage with the identified target audiences. The sections below detail a comprehensive series of measures that will be dynamically adapted to take into consideration the changes in stakeholder profiles and potential use of results during the project lifetime.

3.2 Material

All dissemination material will be high-quality visuals and content, which the consortium monitors continuously.

Project documentation

These are the project deliverables, reports and other materials explaining technical outcomes, APIs, architectures, models, recommendations. In line with the European Open Access Principles, all project documentation in the “public” category will be made available on the project website and public repository.

Guidelines

The Open Call application kit is the essential guidelines addressed for the Open Call candidates. It is published online on the project website and shared in an open repository.

- Open call document kit (Open Access link):
https://zenodo.org/record/4297330/files/OC%20Guideline_v1.pdf

Digital channels

COVID-X Dissemination on digital channels focuses on open access and interactive exchange with stakeholders.

Open Access to Research

In line with the recommendations and requirements from The European Commission, COVID-X adheres the principle of Open Access to Research. It will facilitate an online repository to manage and publish material with different access permissions, which will include open access to peer-reviewed publications, shareable scientific research data, and other types of material generated by the project. The project will make use of [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org/communities/covid-x) as a reference (<https://zenodo.org/communities/covid-x>), where it is possible to deposit both publications and data, while providing tools to link them. In addition, all peer-reviewed publications will be published on the Open Research Europe portal.

Q&A

COVID-X websites include a direct email contact address (info@covid-x.eu) where all inquiries can be addressed. The project coordinator directs the messages to the concerned partners. In addition, a FAQ section on the website will be created for regular problem solving.

4. NEXT STEPS

This deliverable sets the preliminary approach and tools for the Dissemination and Communication strategy of COVID-X project. It overviews all outreach material delivered at M1 (November 2020).

Moreover, the defined dissemination and communication plans set clear KPI objectives for all outreach activities. The COVID-X stakeholders targeted are clearly identified and these groups are used for specific outreach actions via the set tools, the channels, and platforms.

Given the changing project context that is especially linked to the evolution of the coronavirus situation in Europe, all outreach material (including the website, promotional material, selected channels of communication etc.) will evolve throughout the project. This iterative process enables to target the right stakeholders, to provide relevant information and to use the most adapted outreach channels, which is crucial to reach out a critical mass.

The Dissemination and Communication plan is a common route map for the COVID-X consortium since all partners are actively involved in promoting the COVID-X Program on local, national, and European levels.

ANNEX 1 – PRIVACY POLICY

The COVID-X project is committed to protecting your privacy and is developing technology that gives you the most powerful and safe online experience. This Statement of Privacy applies to the Web Site of the H2020 COVID-X project (Grant Agreement 101016065) and governs data collection and usage. The Website falls under the responsibility of the COVID-X Consortium and is concerned with the dissemination and exchange of information about the research conducted in the course of the project and the outcome of this work. By using the Web Site of the COVID-X project, you consent to the data practices described in this statement.

1. POLICY SCOPE

This Privacy Policy applies to this Website www.covid-x.eu/ and it applies regardless of whether you use a computer, mobile phone, tablet, TV or other device.

2. PERSONAL DATA THAT THIS WEBSITE COLLECTS PROVIDED BY YOU AND HOW WE USE IT

Unless stated otherwise in detail in the relevant sections of the Website, Personal Data generated from the use of our Website is processed as follows:

(i) Contact via electronic mail (e-mail)

Should you choose to communicate with us via an email, we invite you to provide your name, as well your mailing address. Please note that your name and mailing address is the only data we collect required for the specified purpose. Without this information we are unable to answer your message and address it to you personally. The legal basis for processing Personal Data for the purposes set out in this Section 2 is art. 6(1)(b) of GDPR as the processing is necessary for the response to requests from the interested party.

(ii) Social Media

Some of our webpages use social plug-ins from other organizations (such as Twitter's retweet function). These other organizations may receive and use personal data about your visit to our sites or apps. If you browse our Website or view content on our apps, information they collect may be connected to your account on their site. For more information on how these organizations use personal data, please read their privacy policies.

(iii) Site visitation tracking

We use Google Analytics (GA) to track user interaction and for statistical reasons. We use this data to determine the number of people using our site, to better understand how they find and use our web pages and to see their journey through the website.

Although GA records data such as your geographical location, device, internet browser and operating system, none of this information personally identifies you to us. Your computer's IP address is

anonymized by GA services and cannot be used to personally identify you. We consider Google to be a third party.

GA makes use of cookies, details of which can be found on Google's developer guides. For your information, our Website uses the analytics.js implementation of GA. Disabling cookies on your internet browser will stop GA from tracking any part of your visit to pages within this website.

3. HOW WE STORE YOUR PERSONAL DATA

If you submit your contact details via the preferred email message, the only personal data will be stored is your name and email address we receive from you. We will not share your contact details with no one and will be securely stored by COVID-X with access only by authorized personnel. This is currently the only occasion where personal data will be stored by this Website.

We utilize state-of-the-art technology to store your data. The following safeguards are used, for example, to protect your personal data from misuse or any form of unauthorized processing:

- Access to personal data is restricted to a limited number of authorized persons for the stated purposes.
- The IT systems used for processing data are technically isolated from other systems to prevent unauthorized access and hacking.
- Access to these IT systems is constantly monitored to detect and prevent misuse in the early stages.

4. HOW LONG WE WILL KEEP YOUR PERSONAL DATA FOR

We will keep your personal information only for as long as it is relevant and useful for the intended purpose for which it was originally collected, or as required by law.

5. COOKIES AND THIRD PARTY – COOKIES

Cookies are small text files that can be used by websites to make a user's experience more efficient. Our Website does not collect any cookies apart from the necessary ones.

You reserve the right to set up your browser to warn you before accepting cookies, or you can simply set it to refuse them, although you may not have access to all the features of this website if you do so. See your browser 'help' button for how you can do this. You do not need to have Cookies on to use or navigate through many parts of this Website. Remember that if you use different computers in different locations, you will need to ensure that each browser is adjusted to suit your Cookie preferences.

6. DATA BREACHES

We will report any unlawful data breach of your data within 72 hours of the breach if it is apparent that personal data stored in an identifiable manner has been stolen.

7. YOUR RIGHTS AS DATA SUBJECT WITH RESPECT TO YOUR PERSONAL DATA

Under the General Data Protection Regulation [Articles 15-21], you have a number of important rights free of charge. In summary, those include rights to:

Right of access:

You have the right to be aware and verify the legitimate nature of the processing. So, you have the right to access your personal data and receive additional information about how we process it.

Right to rectification:

You have the right to study, correct, update or modify your personal data by contacting COVID-X at the info@covid-x.eu.

Right to erasure (Right to be forgotten):

You have the right to request deletion of your personal data when we process it on your consent or in order to protect our legitimate interests. In all other cases (such as, where there is a contract, obligation to process personal data legally required, or public interest), this right is subject to specific restrictions or shall not exist, as the case may be.

Right to restriction of processing:

You have the right to request a restriction of the processing of your personal data in the following cases: (a) when the accuracy of the personal data is contested and until the accuracy is verified (b) when you oppose the deletion of your personal data and request the restriction of their use instead, c) when personal data are not needed for processing purposes, they are however required for the establishment, exercise, or defense of legal claims, and (d) when you object to the processing and the decision on your objection to processing is pending.

Right to object to processing:

You have the right to object at any time to the processing of your personal data where, as described above, the processing is based on the legitimate interests we pursue as data controllers, as well as, for the purposes of direct marketing and consumer profiling, if applicable.

Right to data portability:

You have the right to receive your personal data free of charge in a format that allows you to access, use, and edit them with commonly used editing methods. You also have the right to ask us, in case it is technically feasible, to transmit the data directly to another controller. Your right to do so exists for the data you have provided to us and is processed by automated means based on your consent or for the execution of a relevant contract.

Right to withdraw your consent:

In cases where processing is based on your consent, you have the right to withdraw it without affecting the lawfulness of processing based on consent prior to its withdrawal.

If you would like to exercise any of those rights, please:

- contact us using our Contact details below
- let us have enough information to identify you,
- let us have proof of your identity and address, and
- let us know the information to which your request relates.

8. TIME LIMITS FOR COMPLIANCE WITH YOUR RIGHTS AS DATA SUBJECT

We make every effort to comply with all requests within 30 days. However, this period may be extended for reasons relating to the specific right or complexity of your request.

9. DATA CONTROLLER AND CONTACT DETAILS

The data controller of this website is:

AUSTRALO INTERINNOV MARKETING LAB SL (“AUSTRALO”), a Private Company established in Spain

Whose registered office is at:

AUSTRALO INTERINNOV MARKETING LAB SL,

established in CL POMPEU, FABRA 1 2 4, CASTELLDEFEL 08860, Spain, VAT number: ESB67553677,

Email: contact@australo.org

All questions, comments and requests regarding this Privacy Policy may be also addressed to the following Contact details to contact@australo.org com or post address to our Company.

10. HOW TO COMPLAIN

We hope that we can resolve any query or concern you raise about our use of your Data. However, if you believe that we have not responded in an appropriate manner to your complaints or concerns, the General Data Protection Regulation also gives you the right to lodge a complaint with your local data protection or supervisory authority, in particular in the European Union (or European Economic Area) state where you work, normally live or where any alleged infringement of data protection laws occurred.

11. CHANGES TO OUR PRIVACY POLICY

This privacy policy may change from time to time in line with legislation or industry developments. We will not explicitly inform our clients or website users of these changes. Instead, we recommend that you check this page occasionally for any policy changes.

ANNEX 2 – TERMS OF USE

Welcome to our Website.

Your access to and use of this Website is subject to these Website Terms of Use. Please read them carefully before accessing or using this Website.

1. DEFINITIONS

COVID-X (COVID eXponential Programme), herein referred as “The project”, is a 24-month IA project that addresses the topic SC1-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020-2B.

“Materials” refer to all information, content, data, documents (e.g. white papers, brochures, datasheets, FAQs, templates, press releases, etc.), downloads, files, text, images, photographs, graphics, videos, webcasts, publications, tools, resources, software, code, programs, applications and products made available or enabled via the Website.

The term “The Communication Leader”, otherwise stated as ‘us’ or ‘we’, refers to the owner and creator of the Website <http://www.covid-x.eu/> (collectively referred to herein below as this “Website”), in order to provide information to its users.

AUSTRALO INTERINNOV MARKETING LAB SL (www.australo.org) is the assigned Communication Leader of the Project, based on the 101016065 Grant Agreement. Based on this Grant Agreement, The Communication Leader is responsible for coordinating the communication activities related to the Project’s expected results, including the creation and management of the Website or any other Materials included in it.

The term ‘you’ refers to the visitor of our Website.

2. SCOPE

These Website Terms and Conditions (these “Terms” or these “Website Terms and Conditions”) contained herein, shall govern your use of this Website, including all pages within this Website. These Terms apply in full force and effect to your use of this Website and, by using this Website, you expressly accept all terms and conditions contained herein in full. You must not use this Website, if you have any objection to any of these Website Terms and Conditions.

3. YOUR USE OF THE WEBSITE

You agree to use the Website and its contents only for purposes that are permitted by the Terms of Use and any applicable law, regulation or generally accepted practices or guidelines in the relevant jurisdictions.

You specifically agree not to access (or attempt to access) any of the Materials, through any automated means (including use of scripts or web crawlers), or by hacking, password mining or other means. You agree that you will not engage in any activity that interferes with or disrupts the Website (or the servers and networks, which are connected to or accessible through the Website).

You also agree to use the functionalities available in the Website only to access, download, utilize, post, send or receive Materials in an appropriate manner.

You may view, download for caching purposes only, and print Material from the Website for your own personal use, subject to the restrictions set out below and elsewhere in these Terms and Conditions.

You must not use this Website to copy, store, host, transmit, send, use, publish or distribute any Material, which consists of (or is linked to) any spyware, computer virus, Trojan horse, worm, keystroke logger, rootkit or other malicious computer software. You must not conduct any systematic or automated data collection activities (including without limitation scraping, data mining, data extraction and data harvesting) on or in relation to this Website without the Communication Leader's express written consent. You also agree not to use any Materials in a manner that infringes any Intellectual Property Rights or rights of any party, not to reproduce or utilize in other electronic or printed publications. The graphic as well as technical design and all content as well as pictures used in this online presentation are protected by copyright.

You also agree not to use Website's domain name as a pseudonymous return e-mail address; not to disrupt, interfere or inhibit any other user from using and enjoying the Website or other affiliated or linked sites, or the Materials; and not to use any Materials in a manner that infringes any Intellectual Property Rights or rights of any party;

4. COPYRIGHT AND INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

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Except as permitted by the copyright law applicable, you may not reproduce or communicate any of the content on this Site, including files downloadable from this website, without the written permission of the copyright owner.

5. TRADEMARKS, TRADE NAMES AND LOGOS

All trademarks, trade names and logos appearing in the Website are the property of their respective owners and are protected by the international copyright and trademark laws. You agree not to defame or disparage the Project and all trademarks, trade names or logos included in the Website or in the Materials. Any use of any of the trademarks, trade names and logos appearing throughout the Website without the express written consent of the Project's Communication Leader or the owner of the trademark or name or logo, as applicable, is strictly prohibited.

6. LICENSE TO YOU

The Communication Leader grants you a personal, worldwide, non-assignable, royalty free and non-exclusive license to use the Website solely for the purpose of enabling you to use and enjoy the benefit of the Website and the Materials, in the manner permitted by these Terms of Use. You may not (and you may not permit anyone else to) copy, reverse engineer, create a derivative work of, or decompile or otherwise attempt to extract the source code of the Website or any part thereof, unless this is expressly permitted or required by law, or unless you have been specifically permitted to do so by the Communication Leader. Unless the Communication Leader has given you written permission to do so, you may not

- assign (or grant a sub-license of) your rights to use the Website or the Materials,
- grant a security interest in or over your rights to use the Website or the Materials, or otherwise transfer any of your rights to use them.

7. LINKS TO OTHER INTERNET SITES

The Website may contain links to other internet sites and services that are operated and maintained by third parties or its affiliates. You acknowledge, understand and agree that the Communication Leader will not be responsible or liable, directly or indirectly, for any damage or loss caused or alleged to be caused by or in connection with the use of or reliance on any such content, products or services available on such other sites.

8. CHANGES

The Communication Leader reserves the right to modify, suspend, or discontinue any portion of the Website and Materials at any time, with or without notice. The Communication Leader reserves the right to modify any part of these Terms of Use at any time. Any modifications shall be effective upon posting to the Website. You agree to review these Terms of Use periodically so that you are aware of any such modifications. Your continued use of the Website after any such modifications have been posted shall be deemed your acceptance of any modifications to the Terms of Use. If, at any time, the Terms of Use are not acceptable to you, you should immediately cease use of the Website. You agree that the above-stated standard for notice of modifications is reasonable.

9. LIMITATION OF LIABILITY

The Coordinator shall bear no liability for any direct, indirect, incidental or consequential damages that may be due to the incorrect use of the Website by Users or to any errors, failures, defects or delays in the operation of the Website or in the transmission of information on the Internet through this Website.

8. JURISDICTION

By accessing this Website, and the Materials, you agree that all matters relating to your access to, or use of them, shall be governed by the statutes and laws of Spain (country of the parent company) and European Union, without respect to conflicts of laws principles thereof. Any disputes arising out of the use of this Website will be subject to the exclusive jurisdiction of the Courts of Barcelona, Spain.

10. GENERAL

These Terms of Use shall be governed by, and construed in accordance with, the laws of Spain without regard to its conflicts of law principles. The Communication Leader's performance of these Terms of Use is subject to existing laws and legal process, and nothing contained in these Terms of Use shall derogate the Coordinator's right to comply with law enforcement requests or requirements relating to your use of the Website or information provided to or gathered by the Communication Leader with respect to such use. If any provision of these Terms of Use shall be unlawful, void, or for any reason unenforceable, then that provision shall be deemed severable from these Terms of Use and shall not affect the validity and enforceability of any remaining provisions. These Terms of Use constitute the entire agreement between the parties relating to the subject matter herein, and replace all prior or contemporaneous communications, oral or written.

ANNEX 3 – PRESS RELEASE

17 November 2020

Press Release

Accelerating Data Solutions to save LIVES from COVID-19

The consortium of COVID-X announces the launch of a unique acceleration program in Europe - a **2-year** initiative that will invest **4 million €** to fast-track to market **30+ European data technology solutions** defeating COVID-19 Challenges, facilitating an innovative stack of AI-driven tools.

COVID-19 pandemic is hitting with force. Europe has passed the threshold of **250,000 deaths** since February 2020. COVID-X takes the battle against coronavirus to a new level by bridging the gap between the European digital sector and the healthcare system. The program will **unlock the full capacity of Artificial Intelligence and Data to fight COVID-19**, validating, and scaling up breakthroughs to save lives.

COVID-X will fund **EU Companies** and **Healthcare Providers** to boost data-driven solutions with the power to overcome challenges in Diagnosis, Prognosis, and Follow-up. The funding is invested in products with TRL 7+ and [or in the process of] CE marking, covering two profiles: **single players** (EU Tech SMEs / Start-Ups) validating their solutions at one of COVID-X clinical partners; or **multiplayers** (Tech Provider working with a Healthcare provider that will validate the solution).

The selected projects will join an **Acceleration Program to boost their quick market uptake**. This will include technical support, ethical validation, and business coaching. In addition, participants will have access to the **COVID-X Sandbox**, a one-stop platform to exploit COVID-19 data sources, incorporating general information on data silos, as well as the integration, visualization, and exploratory analysis for easy understanding.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101016065

The program is launching 2 Open Calls and the first Open Call will be launched in early December, with deadline at the end of January 2021.

COVID-X involves a consortium of 10 prominent partners from 7 different countries:

CIVITTA

HUMANITAS
RESEARCH HOSPITAL

For more information

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101016065